

COMBINED PLATE FALLER FOR MES CROPS

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Abstract This paper describes the water and labor resource savings achieved by the development and application of a combined plate faller for mes crops.

Key words: mes crops, combined plate faller, water and labor resource.

In the Strategy for Agricultural Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030, "... The tasks are set out to reduce public participation and establish mechanisms for increasing investment attractiveness, rational use of land and water resources, improving productivity on farms, and improving product quality, which aims to modernize, diversify and increase the flow of private investment capital to support the sustainable growth of the agricultural and food network. Therefore, various reforms are being undertaken in agriculture in the republic to save water and energy in the cultivation of agricultural crops, improve soil productivity and crop yields.

The March 4, 2021, issue of the United Nations Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women and the Elimination All Forms of Discrimination against Women and the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women and the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women and the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women and the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women and the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women and the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women. In these areas, melon crops are cultivated in a variety of ways. One of the most effective methods of cultivating crops in our country is to plant crops under a plate. The resulting embryo was allowed to develop in nutrients and then inserted into her womb, where it was implanted. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) Currently, planting crops under a film

is not mechanized in the republic and is now being carried out by hand because specialized equipment is not manufactured. This, in turn, causes a sharp increase in labour costs and other expenses, and the solution is a pressing scientific problem. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to support more than the gec of Jehovah's Witnesses. In this case, the planting seasons will not only vary, but also their planting schemes will vary. This requires various film-dropping devices that comply with these conditions and fields.

Due to the soil climate of our country, it is necessary to develop a plate-dropping device that matches the regions and seasons where crops are cultivated.

In an effort to solve this current scientific problem, a preliminary constructive scheme of a combined film faller has been developed by us. The constructive scheme of the combined plate drop place is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Constructive scheme of a combined plate drop

Combined plate dropper rama consists of 1.ossetia device 2, floor lift 3, elastic mosquito wheel 4, plate hook 5, elastic pipe hook 6, clicking wheel 7 and burrowing 8.

In the technological process of a combined plate dropper, a floor is removed using a floorhead 2 installed in its front, followed by an elastic mosquito gallbladder that grinds and smoothes the cuts on the top surface of the 3 floors, and the clicking

wheels shed the frames on 6 plates and elastic pipe hooks to the floor surface. Burlaps on both sides of the bed film, which is embedded on the surface of the floor, are thrown away by the soil.

The advantages of the proposed combined plate dropper are that the work organs installed on the device are also able to be adjusted to the necklace and are explained by the installation of an elastic mosquito wheel. It will be possible to obtain a floor of different sizes by changing the working organs in the device frame to different widths. The elastic mosquito wheel mounted on it is also able to expand to the chest, efficiently grinding the cuts on the floor and densifying the soil relatively. In our country, melon crops are grown by obtaining floors of different sizes depending on soil climatic conditions. As a result, this device is suitable for all conditions and has the ability to obtain quality floors of various sizes and to clean the soil efficiently and fill the film.

By applying the proposed combined plate dropplace, 50% of water consumption and 60% of labor costs will be reduced. There is also the possibility of filling the film with this device in thermos method.